

The Impact of Personality Traits on the Work Motivation of Western Expatriate Employees: Exploring Perspective of Local Leaders and Western Expatriates Working in the Oil and Gas Sector of the UAE

¹Hamad Al Naqbi

²Tasfoura Dilawer
ADNOC

Abstract:- The study evaluated the impact of personality traits of local leaders on Western employee motivation in the UAE and explored the perspectives of both local leaders and Western employees working in the UAE oil and gas industry. For the attainment of this goal, the study relied on a mixed approach of data collection that include both qualitative and quantitative data. The researcher collected quantitative data through surveys to check the impact of local leaders' personality traits on Western employee work motivation and considered the 5 personality trait theory. The quantitative data was analysed using descriptive analysis and regression analysis techniques. The research outcomes disclosed that leaders with openness and extroversion personality traits, positively influence Western employee motivation levels. However, it is found that conscientiousness has a positive, but insignificant impact on Western employee motivation. Agreeableness is positively related to employee motivation while neuroticism hurts Western employee motivation with insignificant effect. Qualitatively collected data were analysed using content analysis and it is found that all personality traits of local leaders are positively associated with Western employee motivation except conscientiousness. The research outcomes of content analysis disclosed that when leaders are excessively conscientious, it may result in employee demotivation and they may feel micromanaged. The study based on research outcomes provides certain recommendations to improve the impact of local leaders' personality traits on Western employee motivation.

Keywords:- Personality Traits, Western Employee Motivational Level, and Five Personality Traits Theory.

I. INTRODUCTION

Globalisation has made the management of human resources more complex and demanding due to the increasing ratio of diversity (Ghani, Younus & Bahry, 2016). At the same time, employee motivation has become one of the major concerns of organisations in the global business world, as motivated employees give their best to

ensure the survival of the organisation by offering methods and goals for the attainment of the organisational mission (Al-Ghazo & Al-Anazi, 2016). Leadership plays a critical role in managing human resources efficiently by handling their issues and responding to their needs in the working environment. Leaders who have an understanding of the personality traits of different individuals can use this understanding to improve their leadership skills and effectiveness. Where leaders need to understand the personality traits of employees, it is also necessary that the leaders' personality traits are evaluated as well, as these traits play a significant role in improving the motivational level of Western employees. UAE's oil and gas sector is one of the most culturally diverse sectors as the majority of the work is being done by Western employees. For example, most of the employees performing technical duties and executing specialised tasks are from Western culture. When companies deal with a diversity of employees, it becomes crucial for them to understand the cultural and personality differences to keep them motivated (Almazrouei, Zacca and Alfayez, 2020).

Though multiple studies (Ahmad et al., 2021; Suutari & Riusala, 2001; He et al., 2022) have been conducted to discuss the impact of leadership styles on expatriates, the literature lacks many have discussed the impact of employee personality traits on their motivational level, but the research lack in discussing the impact of local leaders' personality traits on Western employee motivation, most specifically in the context of UAE and Western employees. Thus, this research aims to fill this gap by identifying the role of personality traits of local leaders on the motivational level of Western employees while using the 5 Personality trait theory. The study will be beneficial for oil and gas industry employees and leaders of the UAE, as the outcomes will enhance the understanding of different personality traits of local leaders and how those traits impact Western employees' motivational levels.

Considering the existing gap in the research and developed aim, three certain objectives to reach the research aim have been defined the first objective of the research is to

critically evaluate the personality traits of UAE's local leaders in the oil and gas industry of the UAE. The second objective of the study is to evaluate the impact of five personality traits of local UAE leaders on the motivational level of Western employees in the country's oil and gas industry. However, the last objective of the research is to provide some suggestions to local leaders to improve certain personality traits that can give better results in terms of Western employee motivation.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This study employs the theory of the big five personality traits to determine how individual differences in these traits influence the motivation of Western employees. Amiability, extroversion, introspection, neuroticism, and openness are the five personality traits. It is commonly believed that attributes are relatively stable over time and in various contexts. According to this hypothesis, characteristics are frequently stable and illustrative of behaviour. Extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness to experience are the five most stable and predictive personality traits, according to the personality trait theory. Employers in the oil and gas industry may be able to identify the most qualified candidates for open positions by analysing the interaction between these five characteristics. Nevertheless, the Theory of Personality Traits has numerous applications outside of human resources.

According to the characterization theory, personalities consist of a collection of defining characteristics (Bordwell & Carroll, 2012). These characteristics are crucial for motivating work employee behaviour in human resource management, leaders can use a variety of attributes to influence employee behaviour and capitalise on them. Personality is a collection of characteristics that determine an individual's identity (Gutmann, 2009). People are most valuable to an organization when they contribute to its achievement of objectives. While there are laws and regulations in place to encourage employees to meet company objectives, they fall short of the impact that excellent character traits can have. Failure to do so can have a profoundly demoralizing impact on the morale of the personnel.

Bhatti et al. (2014) made an effort to determine how a person's personality traits affected their job performance and their ability to adapt to a new environment. The analysis of the five major personality traits revealed that the characteristics of expatriates facilitate cultural adaptation and job performance abroad. The study examined the five personality traits from the perspective of workers: conscientiousness, agreeableness, extroversion, openness, and neuroticism. It has been shown that expatriates with conscientiousness-related skills are more likely to acclimate positively to their new environments. In contrast, Judge et al. (2002) analysed leadership characteristics and found that leaders whose behaviour demonstrates extroversion are more likely to nurture a productive workplace culture. Extroverted leaders are known for their exuberance,

sociability, and outspokenness. They facilitate open dialogue, provide assistance to Western employees, and encourage them to participate. When employees in the West feel like they belong on the team, have a voice, and are valued by their supervisor and colleagues, they are more motivated. Thomas (2010), on the other hand, argued that the extraversion of leaders in Western societies was detrimental to the employees. Cultural intelligence plays an important role in the effective administration of personnel from Western cultures, according to the research. By imposing their will on everyone, a dictatorial supervisor could make Western employees feel insecure and stifled. When reducing extroverted executives, it is essential to bear in mind that this may hurt employee morale. Sun and Zuo (2023) discussed the concept of employees motivation and stated it as a driver of organisational performance, the study discussed that the literature lacks in highlighting the factors that can be effective in motivating employees, the study attempted to fill this gap by discussing the factors that are most effective in motivating employees. The purpose of the authors was to unleash the factors that could be used to motivate employees and boost their morale. The authors discussed a holistic approach to determining employee motivation and considered both organisational and individual factors. The study found that extroversion and agreeableness are the personality traits that contribute significantly to the employee conscientiousness, individuals who pursue extroverted personalities tend to build social interaction with their peers. Further, individuals with extroverted personality traits tend to seek growth opportunities. This means that leaders with a quality of extroversion tend to build good relationships with their employees and also seek to have growth by building good relationships with them.

Distinctively, Van Woerkom and De Reuver (2009) shed light on conscientiousness as a personality trait of individuals that has a significant influence on employees' motivation. It is found that conscientious individuals hold the ability to inspire others to perform beyond their set expectations by offering standards. Individuals with a high level of conscientiousness are organized, dependable, and goal-oriented. They establish clear objectives, give disciplined advice, and exhibit a strong work ethic. Such individuals may boost their motivation at work by instilling a sense of purpose, direction, and accountability into other individuals as well. This means that leaders with the trait of extroversion tend to motivate their employees because only those individuals who contain the ability to inspire others tend to encourage others to give their best. The trait of conscientiousness in leaders is extremely important because leaders with such traits tend to set high standards for employees and expectations for their teams. This means conscientiousness leaders can motivate their employees to excellence and ask them to give their best. Conscientious leaders lead by example which may motivate Western employees. Contrarily, Ieda (2023) found that overly rigorous or perfectionistic leaders with high conscientiousness may create a work atmosphere characterized by excessive pressure or micromanagement, which might hamper the work motivation of expatriate staff.

Umer, Fizza, and Abdul Rashid (2019) in their research found that transformational leaders hold a trait of agreeableness that makes them conscious of their employees and they care for them and provide support to them to complete their work on time. This support from leaders keeps employees motivated and engaged and they perform their duties efficiently. Agreeableness is a trait that allows transformational leaders to respect social harmony, they create a cooperative environment that results in knowledge increment leading employees towards improved motivational levels.

According to Arokiasamy and Kim (2020), leaders with strong emotional intelligence can recognize and control their own emotions as well as the emotions of others. They are capable of developing strong interpersonal ties, empathizing with the issues that Western expatriate employees confront, and providing the required assistance. This promotes a pleasant work environment, trust, and motivation.

III. METHODOLOGY

For the attainment of this research goal, a pragmatic research paradigm has been utilised. Considering the pragmatic view, the data was collected using the mixed method, which contains both quantitative and qualitative data collection. The reason for selecting this data collection approach was its appropriateness to the research aim. For example, the research aims to evaluate the perception of both local leaders and Western employees regarding the

personality traits of local leaders. Hence, to gain insights into the perception of local leaders, an interview data collection technique was used and interviews with 8 leaders working in the oil and gas industry of the UAE were conducted. On the contrary, the survey questionnaire was distributed to 100 Western employees to collect quantitative data. The interviews were based on open-ended questions while the survey was based on closed-ended statements.

The interviews conducted with local leaders helped me understand their perspective related to personality traits and their impact on Western employees while gaining some suggestions to improve certain traits to improve Western employee motivation. However, surveys unleashed the perspectives of Western leaders regarding the impact of personality traits of local leaders on the motivational level of Western employees. The perspectives of local leaders were analysed and described using a content analysis approach while survey data were analysed using regression analysis to clearly show the impact of each personality trait on Western employee motivation. The outcomes of both interviews and surveys were checked for their alignment and suggestions were made for local leaders to improve the personality traits that are more important to Western employees to improve their motivational level.

➤ *Data Analysis and Discussion*

- *Descriptive Analysis*

Table 1 Descriptive Analysis

	N	Mean	Mode	Median	Std.Deviation
WEM	100	1.74	2	2	0.440844002
OP	100	1.89	2	2	0.49020713
CON	100	2.15	2	2	0.479372485
EXV	100	2.07	2	2	0.57304785
AGR	100	2.4	2	2	1.063632047
NEU	100	2.27	2	2	0.679497735

Source: Data Analysis

The above statistics summarise the data from which the outcomes can be easily understood. From the above table, it can be assessed that the mean value is 2, which means the average of the data is 2. The mode value for the first two variables Western employee motivation and openness is 1.74 and 1.89 respectively while 2.15 for consciousness, 2.07 for extroversion, 2.4 for agreeableness, and 2.27 for neuroticism is between 1 to 2, which means the majority either strongly agreed or agreed with the statements relevant to each personality trait of local leaders. Further, the

standard deviation is a measure of deviation and indicates the variability level of the data from reality. For example, a value of 0.44 indicates that deviation is close to the mean value and there are fewer chances that the outcomes will variate from reality. On the other hand, the value of 1.0636 communicates that there is a greater chance that the data can variate from reality.

➤ *Regression Analysis*

Table 2 Regression Statistics

Multiple R	0.827727
R Square	0.685133
Adjusted R Square	0.668385
Standard Error	0.253865
Observations	100

Source: Data Analysis

The above regression table explains the relationship between Western employee motivation and the personality traits of local leaders in the UAE oil and gas industry. For example, the value of multiple R indicates the correlation between the dependent variable, which is Western employee motivation and independent variables (openness, extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and neuroticism). For example, Multiple R represents the multiple correlation coefficient. Multiple R measures the direction and strength of the linear relationship between the dependent variable (Western employee motivation) and independent variables (personality traits of local leaders in the UAE oil and gas industry). The above statistics disclosed that multiple R is equal to 82.77%, this value indicates that Western employee motivational levels and local leaders' personality traits are strongly correlated.

The R Square explains the portion of the variance in the term employee motivation that is explained by the

personality traits. The greater value indicates that the higher level of variance has been explained by the independent variables. The R square value of 0.685133 indicates that the personality traits are successfully explaining the work motivation of employees by 68.5%.

Adjusted R Square considering the sample size and number of independent variables provides a conservative estimate of the variable explained by the independent variable. The adjusted R square communicates that around 66.8% of the variance in employee motivation has been explained by the personality traits of local leaders working in the UAE's oil and gas industry. The value of standard error is 0.253865 which indicates the average deviation between the personality traits and Western employee motivation.

➤ *Anova*

Table 3 ANOVA Table

	df	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	5	2.636391	40.90771	3.75E-22
Residual	94	0.064447		
Total	99			

Source: Data Analysis

The above table indicates that there were total 5 numbers of independent variables (OP, CON, EXV, AGR, and NEU) used for this research to check their impact on Western employee motivation. The F value of 40.90771 and P value of 3.75E-22 in the table communicated that the independent variables such as five personality traits are signs explaining the dependent variable. The ANOVA table

explained the overall significance of the regression model and explained that the regression model is effective in explaining the impact of different personality traits on the workplace motivation of Western employees within the oil and gas industry of the UAE.

➤ *Coefficient Table*

Table 4 Coefficient Table

	Coefficients	t Stat	P-value
Intercept	2.586797	14.21362	3.8E-25
OP	0.355908	4.219634	5.64E-05
CON	-1.23059	-9.63065	1.12E-15
EXV	0.513932	4.161142	7.01E-05
AGR	0.092843	1.666193	0.099004
NEU	-0.07064	-0.80193	0.424617

Source; Data Analysis

The coefficient table is one of the best statistical tools that help define the impact of each independent variable separately on the dependent variable (western employee motivation). In other words, the table explains the estimated impact of each personality trait on employee motivation when all other factors are constant. The intercept value of 2.586797 and the P-value of 3.8E-25 indicates that the intercept is strongly significant. The table communicates the coefficient value of openness is 0.355908, which communicates that an increase in a single unit of openness tends to enhance Western employee motivation by 35.59%, while the P-value of 5.64E-05 communicates that the relationship between these two variables is significant.

The coefficient value of conscientiousness is -1.23059 indicating that a unit increase in CON will result in decreasing the employee motivational level by 123.059% while the P-value of 5.64E-05 disclosed a significant relationship between both variables.

The extraversion personality trait of local leaders has a positive and significant relationship with Western employee motivation as the results communicated that the coefficient value of EXV is 0.513932, while the P-value of 7.01E-05, which means the increase in EXV will improve the motivational level of western employees by 51.39%.

The research outcomes indicated that agreeableness has a value of 0.092843, which means an increment in agreeableness will enhance the employee motivation level

by 9.28%, which is a minor change. However, the P-value for AGR is 0.099004 which is relatively higher than 0.05, this means the relationship between these variables is not significant.

The coefficient for neuroticism is -0.07064 indicating that the increment in the one unit of NEU will decrease the western employee motivation level by 7.06%. However, the relationship between these variables is not statistically significant as the P-value of the variable is 0.424617 which is far higher compared to 0.05.

IV. CONTENT ANALYSIS

When managers were asked about the impact of their local personality traits on the work motivation of Western employees, Manager 3 asserted,

“I have observed that a single personality trait has both positive and negative influence on Western employee's motivation. The influence will be positive or negative is dependent on the level of trait it is practised and on the way an individual perceives it.”

➤ *Respondent 4 Commented,*

“I observed that an extrovert leader due to his abilities to be outgoing, assertive, and energetic contains some attributes of being enthusiastic and social that have a positive influence on the work motivation of expatriates.”

➤ *Contrarily, Manager 6 Stated,*

“Extrovert manager overly dominates their employees..... Negatively influences the sense of autonomy and motivation of expatriate employees.”

Two of the managers claimed that conscientiousness and emotional intelligence are the most influential personality traits of local leaders in the UAE that positively influence the working motivation of Western employees if not used for micromanagement. For example, conscientious leaders are detailed oriented, they are responsible and organised and therefore they set high standards to get their means, but if managers behave rightly, this micromanagement decreases employee motivation. Similarly, emotional intelligence is also important to understand the emotions and feelings of Western employees to keep them motivated and engaged, hence, it has a positive influence on employees' workplace motivation.

➤ *Manager 5 Claimed,*

“Leaders open to experiences have the stamina to bear the mistakes of Western expatriates, they are open-minded.....openness is a personality trait that allows us to understand the culturally diverse workforce.”

➤ *Manager 7 Commented,*

“By being open to new things, we provide an opportunity to create new things for our employees and present their ideas.... Openness just does not create an innovative work environment, it motivates Western

employees to give their unique insights while motivating us to engage in continuous learning.”

➤ *Manager 8 Voiced,*

“Being supportive is an immense personality trait that encourages leaders to understand the needs of expatriates and provide them necessary support.... Supportive leaders assist, create a sense of trust and fairness leading employees towards improved motivation.”

V. DISCUSSION

The study aims to evaluate the different perspectives of employees and leaders regarding the impact of local leadership personality traits on the workplace motivation of Western employees. For the attainment of this purpose, the study collected data from both employees through surveys and leaders through interviews. The survey outcomes disclosed that the majority of the employees either agreed or strongly agreed that the personality traits of leaders in the UAE influence their motivational level. However, the perspective on different dimensions of personality change between them. To evaluate the impact of each personality trait of leaders on Western employee motivation, regression analysis was deployed, the quantitative research outcomes disclosed that openness is a personality trait that has a positive and significant relationship with Western employee motivation and the qualitative research outcomes are also aligned with these outcomes. It is found that leaders had a trait of being open to experiences and have a high level of tolerance to accept failures. These leaders are open to new things, innovations and through and provide their employees with room to share their ideas that keep Western employees engaged and feel valued. Open leaders are flexible and understand the needs of culturally diversified employees; hence, they have a positive influence on the motivational level of Western employees. These research outcomes are supported by Ghani, Yunus and Bahry (2016). The authors stated that openness to experience is an important personality trait that influences employee performance. Employee performance is an important measure of the motivational level of employees because employees perform well when they are motivated. Hence, it can be said that the personality trait of openness of a leader enhances the motivational level of Western employees in the UAE oil and gas industry. Further, Kiarie, Maru and Cheruiyot (2017) also commented on the positive impact of leadership's openness to employee motivation. Leaders with openness personality traits tend to be original, curious, open to new ideas, intellectual, and creative, these leaders seem to put their selves in flexible situations and try to learn new things. Leaders with the characteristics to learn new things provide chances for their employees to share their ideas and they also train their employees for skills development that contribute positively to the motivational level of employees. Open leaders encourage their employees to share their ideas that ultimately motivate employees and give them a sense of empowerment.

Reflecting on the conscientiousness personality trait of leaders, the quantitative research outcomes disclosed that this aspect has a negatively significant relationship with Western employee motivation, which means Western employees working in the UAE oil and gas companies are being micromanaged and this behaviour of local leaders is causing to decrease the motivational level of Western employees. On the contrary, the qualitative research outcomes communicated both the positive and negative impact of a leader's conscientiousness on Western employee motivation. For example, though conscientious leaders provide clear direction to their employees and structure their approach, they communicate their expectations to their employees and outline the objectives to provide them with a clear direction and roadmap, there is a huge possibility that their excessive control and habit of keeping a close eye on employee activities has a negative influence on the employee motivational level as they feel oppressed. The qualitative research outcomes unveiled that though conscientiousness has a positive impact on the motivational level of Western employees when leaders extremely control their employees and their conscientiousness takes the shape of micromanagement, the same personality trait becomes negative for Western employee motivation. This means that local leaders operating in the UAE oil and gas industry should maintain a balance in terms of controlling and assisting their employees. The research outcomes are supported by Ieda (2023), as the author stated that conscientiousness taking the shape of micromanagement has a negative influence on employee motivation.

The third personality trait that has been evaluated for its impact on the motivation level of Western employees is to be extroverted. Extroversion is a personality trait of local leaders that has a positive impact on Western employee motivation. Extrovert leaders positively influence the motivational level of employees is an outcome of quantitative data analysis which is also supported by qualitative analysis. The positive outcomes of the extroversion of leaders in terms of Western employee motivation have been supported by Judge et al. (2002). The authors supported extroversion as a positive trait by stating that leaders, who are extroverted, assertive, and energetic, are more likely to foster a productive work environment. They promote open communication and provide resources for Western employees. When employees in the West feel like they belong on the team, have a voice, and are valued by their boss and colleagues, they are more motivated. Sun and Zuo (2023) also supported the positive impact of extroversion on employee motivation by stating it as one of the key actors that contribute to employee motivation. Though the study exerted the impact of the extroverts of an individual on his motivational level, it can be concluded that local leaders with these personality traits tend to value their employees and attempt to build a good relationship with employees that help to motivate them.

The fourth personality trait of leaders that has been chosen to evaluate the impact on Western employee motivation includes agreeableness. The quantitative research outcomes unveiled that leaders with the trait of

agreeableness tend to motivate their Western employees successfully, but the relationship is not statistically significant which means there is no impact of agreeableness with Western employee motivation. These outcomes are not aligned with the qualitative research outcomes. These qualitative results are supported by literature, as Umer, Fizza, and Abdul Rashid (2019) found that agreeableness is a trait of transformational leaders who support their employees and value them. This aspect of transformational leaders makes them effective in motivating employees. Hence, it can be said that agreeableness is a trait that enhances the capabilities of leaders to motivate Western employees so they can give their best. Leaders with agreeableness tend to create a positive and cooperative work environment.

The fifth personality trait is neuroticism which has been selected as an independent variable to check the impact of leaders' personality traits on employee performance. This trait is about emotional intelligence and communicated the level to which leaders handle their emotions such as anger and stress. The research outcomes disclosed that this trait is negatively associated with Western employee motivation, but this relationship is insignificant. This means that quantitative research results disclosed that neuroticism does not have any relationship with Western employee motivation and does not play any role in motivating employees. The outcomes are contrary to the outcomes of qualitative data analysis in the way that qualitative data disclosed that emotional intelligence is key to leadership traits and contributes significantly to the motivational level of Western employees. This means that leaders' neuroticism is a trait that has a negative influence on employee motivational levels. The research outcome that neuroticism is not relevant to employee motivation is supported by (Mat, Jansriboot & Mat, 2019).

VI. PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

The study outcomes contain significant practical implications, such as the oil and gas companies leaders in the UAE will have an enhanced understanding of the specific personality traits that influence the work motivation level of Western employees. An improved understanding of the personality traits that contribute significantly to Western employee motivation can help local leaders develop specific strategies that are particular to motivating Western employees. For example, the research outcomes found that conscientiousness has a negative influence on employee motivation, which means local leaders in the UAE oil and gas industry can develop strategies that do not include over-controlling employees.

The research is beneficial for local leaders in keeping them aware of factors needed to develop cross-cultural leadership skills. The research outcomes will help local leaders in gaining insights into the motivational preferences of employees coming from the West and will help local leaders in tailoring their leadership style according to the Western employees. Further, the researcher will have a practical implication in the recruitment and selection of

leaders such as oil and gas companies for their projects that include Western employees who can hire leaders with certain traits necessary to deal with Western employees.

The research outcomes are also beneficial for oil and gas companies in the UAE as they can be aware of the training and development need of both local leaders and Western employees which can help them in making adjustments. For example, it is found that extroversion plays an important role in Western employee motivation, so the oil and gas companies in the UAE can provide training to their local leaders to enhance this particular trait to better handle and motivate Western employees. The increment in extroversion skills of leaders will enhance the communication process and support building good relationships between Western employees and, local leaders ultimately leading oil and gas companies towards increased performance.

The research outcomes can help oil and gas companies in reconsidering their practices and policies. For example, it is realised that the openness of leaders has a positive influence on employee motivational levels. The oil and gas companies can train their leaders to be more flexible and develop policies and practices to provide the Western employee with an opportunity for work-life balance, providing room for them to share and test their ideas, and promote their well-being. The organisations can develop practices to bear the failures that will not only motivate Western employees to make an effort for the organizations but to also improve their motivational level as well.

By exploring the distinctive perspectives of the personality traits of both Western employees and local leaders about the personality traits that motivate Western employees most, the research contains an ability to better facilitate the understanding and collaboration of cross-cultural communication. The research outcomes contain an ability to appreciate mutual empathy, appreciation, and respect leading oil and gas companies towards a more harmonious work environment and improved level of motivation among Western employees.

Overall, it can be concluded that the practical implications of the research outcomes inform leadership development, organizational policies, recruitment practices, training and development, and the development of training strategies. By understanding the impact of personality traits of local leaders on Western employee motivation, oil and gas companies can create a more engaging and supportive work environment for Western employees that just not lead them towards improved Western employee motivation, but enhanced organizational performance as well.

VII. LIMITATIONS

Due to the dual nature of research such as qualitative data collection and quantitative data collection, the study considered a small sample size of 100 employees and 8 managers working in the oil and gas sector of the UAE. Considering any single method for data collection could

help gather data from a large sample population and the researcher might gain different insights. The study aimed to evaluate the impact of local leaders' personality traits on Western employee motivation in the UAE. Hence, the research outcomes cannot be generalised to other countries as there are cultural differences between the employees of different countries. The study has been conducted within the context of the UAE and the oil and gas industry. Therefore, the findings may not apply to other industries and regions as different sectors have distinctive factors that influence the motivational level of employees.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The finding of research concluded that local leaders' personality traits have an impact on Western employee motivation. The research outcomes of both qualitative and quantitative analysis were aligned and it was found that local leaders' personality traits such as openness and extroversion are positively related to Western employee motivation and have a significant impact. However, the conscientiousness of local leaders is negatively related to Western employees' motivational level and this relationship is significant. On the other side, the research outcomes showed a positive relationship between agreeableness and Western employee motivation, but this relationship is not significant, similarly, neuroticism has a negative relationship with Western employees' motivational level and this relationship is also not significant, which means agreeableness and neuroticism are the personality traits of local leaders that do not have any influence on Western employee motivational level. Cultural contexts and individual characteristics of Western expatriate employees can influence the extent to which certain personality traits impact their willingness to work. Depending on cultural factors such as power distance, collectivism, and communication styles, expatriates from the West may perceive the personality traits of a leader differently. For leaders to have the greatest impact on employee engagement, they must adapt their leadership styles to the specific needs and cultural norms of their workforce.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Ahmad, A. R., ALHAMMADI, A. H. Y., & Jameel, A. S. (2021). National culture, leadership styles and job satisfaction: An empirical study in the United Arab emirates. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(6), 1111-1120.
- [2]. Alghazo, A. M., & Al-Anazi, M. (2016). The impact of leadership style on employee's motivation. *International Journal of Economics and Business Administration*, 2(5), 37-44. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Ali-Alghazo/publication/310585872_The_Impact_of_Leadership_Style_on_Employee%27s_Motivation/links/5831cc7708ae138f1c079f5c/The-Impact-of-Leadership-Style-on-Employees-Motivation.pdf

- [3]. Arokiasamy, J. M., & Kim, S. (2020). When does emotional intelligence function better in enhancing expatriates' cross-cultural adjustment? A study of Japanese PCNs in Malaysia. *Journal of Global Mobility: The home of expatriate management research*, 8(1), 67-84.
- [4]. Awais Bhatti, M., Mohamed Battour, M., Rageh Ismail, A., & Pandiyan Sundram, V. (2014). Effects of personality traits (big five) on expatriates adjustment and job performance. *Equality, Diversity and Inclusion: An International Journal*, 33(1), 73-96.
- [5]. Ayub, M. U., Kanwal, F., & Kausar, A. R. (2019). Developing knowledge creation capability: The role of big-five personality traits and transformational leadership. *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences (PJCSS)*, 13(1), 30-61.
- [6]. Bordwell, D., & Carroll, N. (Eds.). (2012). *Post-theory: Reconstructing film studies*. USA: University of Wisconsin Pres.
- [7]. Ghani, N. M. A., Yunus, N. S. N. M., & Bahry, N. S. (2016). Leader's personality traits and employees job performance in public sector, Putrajaya. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 37, 46-51. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(16\)30091-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(16)30091-0)
- [8]. Gutmann, A. (2009). *Identity in democracy*. UK: Princeton University Press.
- [9]. He, G., Wang, Y., Zheng, X., Guo, Z., & Zhu, Y. (2022). Linking paternalistic leadership to work engagement among Chinese expatriates: a job demand-resource perspective. *International Journal of Manpower*, 43(4), 889-909.
- [10]. Ieda, H. (2023). *Redesigning Leadership In China: A Practical Guide For Japanese Executives Leading Chinese Sales Teams*. https://www.uniselinus.education/sites/default/files/2023_03/Ieda_Hidekazu.pdf
- [11]. Judge, T. A., Bono, J. E., Ilies, R., & Gerhardt, M. W. (2002). Personality and leadership: a qualitative and quantitative review. *Journal of applied psychology*, 87(4), 765. <https://psycnet.apa.org/buy/2002-15406-013>
- [12]. Judge, T. A., Bono, J. E., Ilies, R., & Gerhardt, M. W. (2002). Personality and leadership: a qualitative and quantitative review. *Journal of applied psychology*, 87(4), 765. <https://psycnet.apa.org/buy/2002-15406-013>
- [13]. Kiarie, M. A. W., Maru, L. C., & Cheruiyot, T. K. (2017). Leader personality traits and employee job satisfaction in the media sector, Kenya. *The TQM Journal*. <https://sci-hub.hkvisa.net/10.1108/TQM-09-2015-0117>
- [14]. Mat, N., Jansriboot, P., & Mat, N. (2019). Big Five Personality, Transformational Leadership, Psychological Safety, and Employee Engagement of Private Sector Employees in Southern Thailand. *Jurnal Pengurusan*, (56), pp. 1-19.
- [15]. Sun, P., & Zuo, X. (2023). The Missing Piece: Incorporating Organizational Factors in Employee Motivation Research. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 25(1), 24-33. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Peng-Sun-104/publication/370602108_The_Missing_Piece_Incorporating_Organizational_Factors_in_Employee_Motivation_Research/links/6459311b5762c95ac38029eb/The-Missing-Piece-Incorporating-Organizational-Factors-in-Employee-Motivation-Research.pdf
- [16]. Suutari, V., & Riusala, K. (2001). Leadership styles in central eastern Europe: Experiences of Finnish expatriates in the Czech Republic, Hungary and Poland. *Scandinavian Journal of Management*, 17(2), 249-280.
- [17]. Van Woerkom, M., & De Reuver, R. S. (2009). Predicting excellent management performance in an intercultural context: A study of the influence of multicultural personality on transformational leadership and performance. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 20(10), 2013-2029. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585190903175589>